

Religious Places & Karmic Events

19 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

There are several posts where people mention that they visited a certain religious place and fell sick- This is what is supposed to happen. When you start your Journey, You are preparing for darshan and nature has its own ways to cleanse you by giving you troubles, firstly on the external basis and then on the soul level.

The same thing happens when you do deep meditations, When you sit for meditation, I see people say I meditate for 2 hours, If you know the time of your meditation then you haven't really done anything. Meditation is a state of timelessness which is beyond kaal, when you go in a state that when you come back, you have to remind yourself, of where I am and you have to remind yourself of your identity again.

When you do deep meditation, there is a huge amount of disconnect between your soul and physical body and that is why you fall sick, Lot of yogis stop eating or limit their diet due to this but this is no other way around that by leaving food you become a yogi, what most people try to do while meditation.

Almost Similar things happen to your body when you visit a religious place and for a moment while you are in that place your soul tries to connect to the supreme and this results in a disconnect to the physical body, What is your body without a soul?

Whenever I visit Haridwar I always tell people, It's not the GPS which tells the location but my whole body as i start to fall sick, Haridwar is the gateway to the sky due to its coordinates on the map—4 places where amrit kalash was Haridwar, Ujjain, Nasik, Praygraj- If you ever draw coordinates straight line you will find a big triangle is formed.

Haridwar or any religious place always have various elements to punish you as these are extremely karmic places where your sin has to be taken off your shoulder by snatching money, pickpocketing, beggars and all these people are there to cleanse you, The presence of such a huge water body can bring huge changes in your life based in which tithi you are planning to visit.

When you come back home and feel ill, this is because your soul experienced a small portion of disconnect from your physical body and will take time to recover, no amount of medicine can cure this, When you go to the mountains try to take a vacation where there are fewer humans, as the whole purpose of a vacation is to find yourself again and sit around doing nothing for hours and meditate, It will be far more religious than visiting a temple where you can't even breathe, that is why shrines were built at hilltop so only few can visit who are in need of such energy, The energy of mountains suits few people only as your head will get heavy, you feel different energy building inside you, the feeling is different as your body is not used to this energy, it feels dizzy and sleepy, and the best travelers are who sleep a lot to adjust to new energy from sky, Just like newborn babies. [Secrets of Temple | by Deepanshu Giri | Medium](#) – Here is another blog related to the same topic- [Curse of Accepting Gifts. – Lunar Astro Vedic Academy](#).

Sometimes, There is too much resistance in your body due to negative feelings that it is unable to adjust to this new energy such as Moon Ketu is a combination where a person does not like to share his feelings but Haridwar is a place where the water and emotions are in abundance which will result into opposite energy and native will feel sick as water energy is trying to flow through his body this is only true for freshwater source. In contrast, if the same combination will visit the seaside then its completely fine.

while people with Moon Rahu who like to share everything with everyone in a twisted way will feel blocked on mountains and go through a series of turn as now mountains require concentration of energy and your soul energy start getting focused on mountains and this might give you a feeling of your true sense that you are alone in this world.

Let me teach you a dictum- Jaimini Sutram says with Ketu in Lagna native will have grey hair prematurely, the reason is the same as native has a disconnect from his physical body and try to live in his own world is why the native become old early.

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19 thoughts on “Religious Places & Karmic Events”

ANJU

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Me ketu in Aries lagna, got old very early , premature grey hair

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